

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

DOCUMENTATION OF RISIS DATASETS VICO (version 5.0)

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1 Basic Characteristics

The VICO data infrastructure (version 5.0) contains geographical, industry and accounting information on companies founded starting from 1/1/1988, which have received at least one Venture Capital (VC) investment starting from 1/1/1998 up to 31/12/2018, operating in the 27 countries of the European Union, plus United Kingdom and Israel and information on their investment deals (e.g. deal date, total amount invested). VICO covers an overall number of 37,863 companies, that have been involved in 54,910 VC investment deals.

The aim of the VICO dataset is to create a unique data infrastructure with a substantial coverage of VC activity in Europe. The current version 5.0 of the VICO dataset extends the previous version 4.0, developed within the RISIS 1 project, by:

- adding VC investments up to 2018 and accounting data up to 2020 (both previously available up to 2014);
- expanding the geographical coverage to EU-27 countries, United Kingdom and Israel (previously limited to 8 countries: Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, United Kingdom and Israel)
- adding a new module with information on the exit activity (i.e. M&As/IPOs) of VICO companies (“Exit Table”);
- adding a new module with information on a sample of equity Crowdfunding (CF) investments in the UK (“Equity CF Table”).

Its uniqueness lies in the overall number of companies, the country coverage, and the extent of information gathered, thanks to the combination of multiple secondary data sources, namely Thompson Eikon, Bureau van Dijk Zephyr, Crunchbase and Bureau van Dijk Orbis.

Services currently offered by the VICO infrastructure allows to address a wide range of research questions concerning the characteristics, the evolution and the role of VC in Europe. It has been widely used by a large academic community to study the peculiarities of the European VC market and the effectiveness of different forms of VC in supporting the performance of European start-ups. Results from academic research based on VICO also attracted the attention of policy makers interested in assessing the impact of policy measures aimed at facilitating access to start-up finance.

The legal name of the operating organization is POLITECNICO DI MILANO, Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, located in VIA LAMBRUSCHINI 4/B, MILANO, 20156, Italy represented by Alessandro Perego, Head of Department (or his authorized representative).

The VICO dataset access manager is Francesca Tenca (francesca.tenca@polimi.it).

2 Database content

2.1 Definition and description of observations

The database includes 37,863 companies founded starting from 1/1/1988, which have received at least one venture capital investment starting from 1/1/1998 up to 31/12/2018, operating in the 27 countries of the European Union, plus United Kingdom and Israel. VICO

provides basic information on 12,015 distinct investors, of which 8,880 Venture Capitalists (VCs) and 2,802 Business Angels (BAs), plus a small percentage of other investors (e.g. crowdfunding, incubators/accelerators...). It also includes 750 equity CF investment deals located in the UK (i.e. the largest equity CF market in Europe) in the period 2011-2018.

Companies and investors have been involved in 54,910 investment deals, for a total of 97,985 observations (as one or more investors can be involved in each single investment round).

The data infrastructure is organized in the following six tables:

1. **Companies**, which contains information on basic companies' characteristics. The unit of observation is the VC-backed company;
2. **Investments**, which contains information on VC deals (e.g. deal date, amount invested, investors involved, ...). The main unit of observation is the VC deal (i.e. the company-date-investor triad);
3. **Investors**, which contains information on basic investors' characteristics. The unit of observation is the investor;
4. **Accounting**, which contains accounting data of VC-backed companies. The main unit of observation is the company-year dyad;
5. **Exits**, which contains information on M&A and IPO deals conducted by VC-backed companies. The main unit of observation is the M&A/IPO deal (i.e. the company-date-acquirer triad).
6. **Equity CF Investments**, which contains information on equity CF deals. The main unit of observation is the equity CF campaign-date dyad.

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

In order to identify companies, investors and investment deals, we considered three main sources of information: Thompson Eikon, Bureau van Dijk Zephyr and Crunchbase.

The data collection process consisted in five main steps:

1. Definition of a unique list of companies and investors from the three source databases and organization of VC investment deals.
2. Data collection and organization of accounting information.
3. Data collection and organization of M&A/IPO activity.
4. Data collection and organization of equity CF investments.
5. Geocoding.
6. Collection of additional information on Corporate VCs.

In what follows, we describe the data collection process in detail.

2.2.1 Definition of a unique list of companies and investors from the three source databases and organization of VC investment deals

After downloading the list of VC deals from the three sources databases, i.e. Thompson Eikon, Bureau van Dijk Zephyr and Crunchbase, a unique list of company names was created through company names disambiguation within the three data sources and VICO version 4.0 dataset, as follows:

1. Download of all VC investment deals from 2010 to 2018 from each source database for the countries covered in VICO. This timeframe includes an overlapping period with VICO version 4.0 (i.e. 2010-2014) to identify possible missing investment deals due to the fact

- that when the original download took place (in March 2015), source databases may not have been completely updated;
2. Disambiguation between new downloaded company names and VICO version 4.0 company names;
 3. Disambiguation of the remaining newly added company names between the three sources databases, before the integration into VICO version 5.0.
 4. Name disambiguation for new investors collected in steps 2 and 3.
 5. Identification and addition of VICO version 4.0 companies' new VC deals (for the period 2015-2018) and addition of VC deals of newly added companies into VICO version 5.0.

To accomplish the name disambiguation, we use automated matching procedures in Excel (e.g. fuzzy matching add-on) and STATA, as well as manual checks.

2.2.2 Data collection and organization of accounting information

For the sample of VC-backed companies, we downloaded from Bureau van Dijk Zephyr Orbis accounting information (balance sheet, income statement and cash-flow) for the period 2012-2020.

For companies that were included in the version 4.0 of the VICO dataset, we updated the accounting information (originally available for the period 2005-2014) to add new accounting data for the 2015-2020 years.

For VC-backed companies added with the version 5.0 of VICO (96% of which received VC investments on or after 2012) we added accounting information for the entire period 2012-2020.

We also double checked the consistency of accounting information for companies included in version 4.0 with the more updated information available in Orbis (as in 2021). This allowed to identify a relative small number of inconsistencies that lead to the elimination of accounting data for less than 10% of VC-backed companies originally included in the version 4.0 of the VICO dataset.

Information on accounting data is available in the Accounting Table of the VICO dataset.

2.2.3 Data collection and organization of M&A/IPO activity

Information on M&A and IPO activity of VC-backed firms has been retrieved from Bureau van Dijk Zephyr database.

For each VC-backed company we downloaded information on (completed or completed assumed) M&A and IPO deals occurred in the period 1998-2017 that involved the focal VC-backed company as target.

We then downloaded information on the deal structure (e.g. deal value, announced and completed dates, acquired stakes), on the characteristics of the target (i.e. acquired) firms (e.g. name, country and industry of operation) and on the characteristics of the acquirer firms (e.g. name, country).

Information on M&A/IPO activity of VC-backed companies is available in the Exits Table of the VICO dataset.

2.2.4 Data collection and organization of equity CF investments

Information on equity CF investments were directly retrieved from Seedrs and Crowdcube platforms, i.e. the two largest equity CF platforms in the UK. The data cover the period 2011-2018 and track all the successful equity CF campaigns launched on these two platforms.

Basic information on CF campaign characteristics and outcome were collected (e.g. target amount, total amount raised, project category, location...). The companies, which successfully performed an equity CF campaign on the two aforementioned platforms were then matched with VC-backed companies (Companies Table) via BvDID number and/or company name, thus identifying a sample of companies located in the UK that have raised VC funding in addition to equity CF.

Information on equity CF investments in the UK is available in the Equity CF Investments Table.

2.2.5 Geocoding

Geocoding (i.e. retrieving latitude and longitude coordinates) of VC-backed companies and investors was accomplished using the RISIS Cortext service. The geocoding is based on the company's city and country (or the company's city, zipcode and country when available).

We manually checked the coordinates for which Cortext returned a confidence level less than 1 or that were not located at the "locality" level, a label available in Cortext output, which identifies that the address is geocoded using the city centroid. When inconsistencies were found, we manually retrieved the coordinates by looking up the focal company's city/zipcode on Google Maps.

We were able to geolocalize the vast majority of the companies and investors (with addresses). On the basis of the geographical coordinates, we associated information on NUTS regions and Functional Urban and Rural Areas.

Geographical information of VC-backed companies is available in the Companies Table of the VICO dataset.

2.2.5 Additional extensions of VICO version 5.0

We performed additional data collection efforts in order to enrich VICO dataset with information on CVC, as follows:

- Classification of Corporate VC investors (CVC) on the basis of their mission (strategic vs. financial objectives) and level of autonomy from their parent company. We did this mainly by searching CVC investors' websites.

Information on CVC strategy and CVC autonomy is available in the Investors Table of the VICO dataset.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

Table 1-6 describe variables names, descriptions and types.

Table 1 – Companies Table

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies
BvDIDnumber	string	Orbis ID for companies
CompanyName	string	Company name
CompanyName_Orbis	string	Company name from Orbis
CompanyOtherNames	string	Other company names
CompanyNation	string	Company country
CompanyCity	string	Company city
CompanyAddress	string	Company address
CompanyZipCode	string	Company ZipCode
CompanyFoundedYear	float	Company year of foundation
NACERev2corecode4digits_Orbis	string	Company NACERev2 core code from Orbis
NACERev2corcodesdes_Orbis	string	Company NACERev2 core code description from Orbis
FirstInvestmentYear	float	Company year of first investment received
CompanyLong	float	Company longitude
CompanyLat	float	Company latitude
CompanyNUTS3Name	string	Name of the company NUTS3
CompanyNUTS3	string	Code of the company NUTS3
CompanyFUAName	string	Name of the company FUA
CompanyFUANUniqueID	string	Cortex ID of the company FUA
CompanyFUACode	string	Code of the company FUA
CompanyRuralName	string	Name of the company Rural Area
CompanyRuralUniqueID	string	Cortex ID of the company Rural Area
CompanyRuralCode	string	Code of the company Rural Area

Table 2 – Investments Table

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies
InvestorID	string	VICO ID for investors
InvestmentDate	float	Date of investment round
InvestmentYear	float	Year of investment round
TotalEquityInvested_round_thEUR	string	Total equity investment in the investment round in thEUR

Table 3 – Investors Tables

Variable	Type	Description
InvestorID	string	VICO ID for investors
InvestorName	string	Investor name

InvestorOtherNames	string	Investor other names according to different data sources
InvestorNation	string	Investor country
InvestorCity	string	Investor city
InvestorLong	float	Investor longitude
InvestorLat	float	Investor latitude
InvestorNUTS3Name	string	Name of the investor NUTS3
InvestorNUTS3	string	Code of the investor NUTS3
InvestorFUAName	string	Name of the investor FUA
InvestorFUAUniqueID	string	Cortext ID of the investor FUA
InvestorFUACode	string	Code of the investor FUA
InvestorRuralName	string	Name of the investor Rural Area
InvestorRuralUniqueID	string	Cortext ID of the investor Rural Area
InvestorRuralCode	string	Code of the investor Rural Area
InvestorType	string	Investor Type
CVC_autonomy	string	Level of autonomy of the CVC from the parent company
CVC_separateWebsite	boolean	Dummy = 1 if the CVC investor has a separate website
CVC_Mission	string	Mission of the CVC: whether the investor pursue strategic or financial objectives (or both), according to the CVC's mission statement

Table 4 – Accounting Table

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies
Year	float	Year to which the accounting data refers to
FixedassetsthEUR	float	Total amount (after depreciation) of non current assets. (Intangible assets+Tangible assets+Other fixed assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ruIntangiblefixedassetsthEUR	float	All intangibles assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TangiblefixedassetsthEUR	float	All tangibles assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
OtherfixedassetsthEUR	float	All other Fixed Assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CurrentassetsthEUR	float	Total amount of current assets. (Stocks+Debtors+Other current assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal
StockthEUR	float	Total inventories. Thousand Euro. Nominal
DebtorsthEUR	float	Trade receivables. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthercurrentassetsthEUR	float	All other current assets. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CashcashequivalentthEUR	float	Detail of other current assets=amount of cash at bank and in hand of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
TotalassetsthEUR	float	Total Assets. (Fixed assets+Current assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal

ShareholdersfundsthEUR	float	Total Equity (Capital+Other shareholders funds). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CapitalthEUR	float	Issued Share capital. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthershareholdersfundsthEUR	float	All shareholders funds not linked with the Issued capital. Thousand Euro. Nominal
NoncurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All long-term liabilities of the company. (Long term debts+Other non current liabilities+Provisions). Thousand Euro. Nominal
LongtermdebththEUR	float	Long-term financial debts to credit institutions (>1Year). Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthernoncurrentliabthEUR	float	All long-term liabilities not related to financial institutions (including Provisions). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ProvisionsthEUR	float	Detail of other non current liabilities=Provisions. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All current liabilities of the company (Loans+Creditors+Other current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal
LoansthEUR	float	Short-term financial debts to credit institutions (<1Year). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CreditorsthEUR	float	All debts to suppliers and contractors. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthercurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All current liabilities not payable to financial institutions nor trade debts. Thousand Euro. Nominal
TotalsharehfundsliabthEUR	float	Total Shareholders Equity and liabilities. (Shareholders funds+Non current liabilities+Current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal to drop
WorkingcapitalthEUR	float	Net working capital (Stocks+Debtors-Creditors). Thousand Euro. Nominal
NetcurrentassetsthEUR	float	Net current assets (Current Assets-Current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal
EnterprisevaluethEUR	float	Sum of the Market capitalisation, the Long term debts and the Loans (to financial institutions) minus the Cash and cash equivalent (for listed companies only). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TurnoverthEUR	float	Total operating revenues (Net sales+Other operating revenues+Stocks variations). Thousand Euro. Nominal
SalesthEUR	float	Net sales. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CostsofgoodssoldthEUR	float	Costs of sold goods, production and services. Thousand Euro. Nominal
GrossprofitthEUR	float	Turnover – Costs of goods sold. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OtheroperatingexpensesthEUR	float	All costs not directly related to the production of goods sold. Thousand Euro. Nominal

OperatingPLEBIThEUR	float	Earnings before interests and taxes (Gross profit – Other operating expenses). Thousand Euro. Nominal
FinancialrevenuethEUR	float	All financial revenues (interests, incomes from shares,..). Thousand Euro. Nominal
FinancialexpensesthEUR	float	All financial expenses (interest charges, write-off financial assets,..). Thousand Euro. Nominal
FinancialPLthEUR	float	Resut from financial activities. (Financial revenues – Financial expenses). Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLbeforetaxthEUR	float	Earnings before taxes. (Operating profit+Financial profit). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TaxationthEUR	float	All taxes paid by the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLaftertaxthEUR	float	Earnings after taxes. (Profit before taxation – Taxation) Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExtrandotherrevenuethEUR	float	All extraordinary revenues and other revenues not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExtrandotherexpensesthEUR	float	All extraordinary expenses and other rexpenses not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExtrandotherPLthEUR	float	All extraordinary and other result not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLforperiodNetincomethEUR	float	Net income for the Year. (Profit after taxation+Extraordinary and other profit). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExportrevenuethEUR	float	Revenues from exports. Thousand Euro. Nominal
MaterialcoststhEUR	float	Detail of the cost of materials used only for goods produced. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CostsofemployeesthEUR	float	Detail of all the employees costs of the company (including pension costs). Thousand Euro. Nominal
DepreciationAmorththEUR	float	Total amount of depreciations and amortizations of the assets. Thousand Euro. Nominal
InterestpaidthEUR	float	Total amount of interest charges paid for shares or loans. Thousand Euro. Nominal
RDexpensesthEUR	float	Total amount of R&D expenses. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CashflowthEUR	float	Profit for period+Depreciation. Thousand Euro. Nominal
AddedvaluethEUR	float	Profit for period+Depreciation+Taxation+Interests paid+Cost of employees. Thousand Euro. Nominal

EBITDAthEUR	float	Operating profit+Depreciation. Thousand Euro. Nominal
Numberofemployees	float	Total number of full time employees of the company

Table 5 – Exits Table

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies
AcqDealNumber	string	Zephyr ID for acquisition deals
Acquirorname	string	Name of the acquirer
Acquirorcountrycode	string	Country code of the acquirer
AcqDealtype	string	Description of the Acquisition Deal with sold ownership
AcqDealvaluethEUR	float	Acquisition Deal value in th EUR
AcquirorBvDIDnumber	string	CompanyBvDID of the acquiror
AcqDate	float	Date in which the Acquisition was completed, otherwise completed assumed, otherwise announced
AcqYear	float	Year in which the Acquisition was completed, otherwise completed assumed, otherwise announced
Acquisition_dummy	boolean	Dummy equal to 1 if the company was acquired (ownership sold > 50%), 0 otherwise
IPODealNumber	string	Zephyr ID for IPO deals
IPODealvaluethEUR	float	IPO Deal value in th EUR
IPODate	float	Date in which the IPO was completed, otherwise completed assumed, otherwise announced
IPOYear	float	Year in which the IPO was completed, otherwise completed assumed, otherwise announced
IPOStockExchange	string	Stock Exchange of the IPO
IPO_dummy	boolean	Dummy equal to 1 if the company went through an IPO

Table 6 –Equity CF Investments Table

Variable	Type	Description
IDEquityCF	string	VICO ID for Equity CF Campaign
CampaignName	string	Name of the Equity CF Campaign
EquityOfferedFirstCampaign	float	Amount of Equity Offered in the First Campaign
PostMoneyFirstCampaign	float	Post money valuation after First Campaign
CampaignDate	string	Date of the Campaign
CampaignYear	float	Year of the Campaign
CampaignAmountRaised	float	Raised amount in the Campaign
CampaignCategory	string	Description of Campaign Category

Platform	string	Name of the platform of the Equity CF Campaign
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

Sectorial classification follows the NACE Rev. 2 classification. The distribution of companies according to the NACE Rev. 2 Main Section is reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Sectorial coverage

NACE Rev. 2 Main Section	N. Companies	Percent
A - Agriculture, forestry and fishing	56	0.21
B - Mining and quarrying	62	0.23
C - Manufacturing	3514	13.25
D - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	176	0.66
E - Water supply; sewerage, waste management	81	0.31
F - Construction	287	1.08
G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	2323	8.76
H - Transportation and storage	256	0.97
I - Accommodation and food service activities	278	1.05
J - Information and communication	10137	38.22
K - Financial and insurance activities	1323	4.99
L - Real estate activities	255	0.96
M - Professional, scientific and technical activities	4957	18.69
N - Administrative and support services activities	1600	6.03
O - Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	9	0.03
P - Education	187	0.71
Q - Human health and social work activities	382	1.44
R - Arts, entertainment and recreation	226	0.85
S - Other service activities	408	1.54
T - Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods and services-producing activities of households for own use	6	0.02
Total	26523	100.00

The population of companies has been restricted to those founded starting from 1/1/1988, which received the first investment starting from 1/1/1998 up to 31/12/2018. Overall, start-ups are relatively young, with a median foundation year of 2008. Table 8 and 9 report the distribution of VC-backed companies by foundation year and year of the first investment received.

Table 8: Distribution of companies by foundation year

Foundation year	N. Companies	Percent
before 1990	374	1.31
1990≤y<1995	1287	4.54
1995≤y<2000	3527	12.43
2000≤y<2005	4946	17.44

2005≤y<2010	5598	19.74
2010≤y≤2015	10197	35.95
after 2015	2436	28.37
Total	28365	100.00

Table 9: Distribution of companies by year of first investment

First Investment Year	N. Companies	Percent
before 2000	1547	4.09
2000≤y<2005	7387	19.51
2005≤y<2010	6100	16.11
2010≤y≤2015	13556	35.80
after 2015	9273	24.49
Total	37863	100.00

As to the temporal coverage of accounting data and M&A/IPO information, they are available respectively from 2005 to 2018 and from 1998 to 2017. Equity CF investments are available from 2011 to 2018.

As to the geographical coverage, the database includes information on the country, NUTS regions (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/regions-and-cities/overview>), Functional Urban and Rural Areas (<https://www.oecd.org/cfe/regional-policy/functionalurbanareasbycountry.htm>) and exact geographical coordinates (i.e. latitude and longitude). The geographical distribution according to the country in which the VC-backed company is located is reported in Table 10.

Table 10: Distribution of companies by country

Country	N. Companies	Percent
Austria	520	1.37
Belgium	873	2.31
Bulgaria	245	0.65
Croatia	67	0.18
Cyprus	70	0.18
Czech Republic	196	0.52
Denmark	883	2.33
Estonia	215	0.57
Finland	1367	3.61
France	6129	16.19
Germany	4562	12.05
Greece	129	0.34
Hungary	523	1.38
Ireland	1036	2.74
Israel	2159	5.70
Italy	1146	3.03
Latvia	178	0.47
Lithuania	146	0.39
Luxembourg	122	0.32
Malta	28	0.07

Netherlands	1665	4.40
Poland	776	2.05
Portugal	495	1.31
Romania	123	0.32
Slovakia	85	0.22
Slovenia	47	0.12
Spain	2282	6.03
Sweden	2172	5.74
United Kingdom	9624	25.42
Total	37863	100.000

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

Table from 11 to 16 report the number of missing values and the percentage of missing values with respect to the total number of observations (i.e. the number of companies, investors and investment deals).

Table11 – Missing information: Companies Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
CompanyID	0	37863	0%
BvDIDnumber	7984	37863	21.08%
CompanyName	0	37863	0%
CompanyName_Orbis	7984	37863	21.08%
CompanyOtherNames	21198	37863	55.98%
CompanyNation	0	37863	0%
CompanyCity	522	37863	1.38%
CompanyAdress	4670	37863	12.33%
CompanyZipCode	4670	37863	12.33%
CompanyFoundedYear	9498	37863	25.08%
NACERev2corecode4digits_Orbis	7984	37863	21.08%
NACERev2corcodesdes_Orbis	7984	37863	21.08%
FirstInvestmentYear	0	37863	0%
CompanyLong	998	37863	2.63%
CompanyLat	998	37863	2.63%
CompanyNUTS3Name	3088	37863	8.15%
CompanyNUTS3	3088	37863	8.15%
CompanyFUAName	1007	37863	2.91%
CompanyFUAUniqueID	1007	37863	2.91%
CompanyFUACode	1007	37863	2.91%
CompanyRuralName	1007	37863	2.91%
CompanyRuralUniqueID	1007	37863	2.91%
CompanyRuralCode	1007	37863	2.91%

Table 12 – Missing information: Investments Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
CompanyID	0	97985	0%
InvestorID	0	97985	0%

InvestmentDate	0	97985	0%
InvestmentYear	0	97985	0%
TotalEquityInvested_round_thEUR	23977	97985	24.47%

Table 13 – Missing information: Investors Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
InvestorID	0	12015	0%
InvestorName	0	12015	0%
InvestorOtherNames	5088	12015	42.35%
InvestorNation	1396	12015	11.62%
InvestorCity	3660	12015	30.46%
InvestorLong	3845	12015	32.00%
InvestorLat	3845	12015	32.00%
InvestorNUTS3Name	6733	12015	56.04%
InvestorNUTS3	6733	12015	56.04%
InvestorFUAName	3901	12015	32.47%
InvestorFUAAUniqueID	3901	12015	32.47%
InvestorFUACode	3901	12015	32.47%
InvestorRuralName	3901	12015	32.47%
InvestorRuralUniqueID	3912	12015	32.56%
InvestorRuralCode	3901	12015	32.47%
InvestorType	681	12015	5.67%
CVC_autonomy	1513	12015	12.59%
CVC_separateWebsite	1532	12015	12.75%
CVC_Mission	1540	12015	12.82%

Table 14 – Missing information: Accounting Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
CompanyID	0	319645	0%
Year	0	319645	0%
FixedassetsthEUR	169493	319645	53.03%
IntangiblefixedassetsthEUR	181858	319645	56.89%
TangiblefixedassetsthEUR	181762	319645	56.86%
OtherfixedassetsthEUR	182112	319645	56.97%
CurrentassetsthEUR	169292	319645	52.96%
StockthEUR	173638	319645	54.32%
DebtorsthEUR	172908	319645	54.09%
OthercurrentassetsthEUR	172138	319645	53.85%
CashcashequivalentthEUR	181284	319645	56.71%
TotalassetsthEUR	169056	319645	52.89%
ShareholdersfundsthEUR	168688	319645	52.77%
CapitalthEUR	169633	319645	53.07%
OthershareholdersfundsthEUR	170452	319645	53.33%
NoncurrentliabilitiesthEUR	170784	319645	53.43%
LongtermdebtthEUR	210330	319645	65.80%
OthernoncurrentliabthEUR	210356	319645	65.81%
ProvisionsthEUR	231849	319645	72.53%

CurrentliabilitiesthEUR	169091	319645	52.90%
LoansthEUR	187101	319645	58.53%
CreditorsthEUR	186352	319645	58.30%
OthercurrentliabilitiesthEUR	184483	319645	57.71%
TotalsharefundsliabthEUR	168899	319645	52.84%
WorkingcapitalthEUR	198968	319645	62.25%
NetcurrentassetsthEUR	193254	319645	60.46%
EnterprisevaluethEUR	314576	319645	98.41%
TurnoverthEUR	226423	319645	70.84%
SalesthEUR	245344	319645	76.76%
CostsofgoodssoldthEUR	297892	319645	93.19%
GrossprofitthEUR	290451	319645	90.87%
OtheroperatingexpensesthEUR	239491	319645	74.92%
OperatingPLEBITthEUR	219347	319645	68.62%
FinancialrevenuethEUR	239746	319645	75.00%
FinancialexpensesthEUR	231899	319645	72.55%
FinancialPLthEUR	219131	319645	68.55%
PLbeforetaxthEUR	219198	319645	68.58%
TaxationthEUR	244117	319645	76.37%
PLaftertaxthEUR	224389	319645	70.20%
ExtrandotherrevenuethEUR	284586	319645	89.03%
ExtrandotherexpensesthEUR	283590	319645	88.72%
ExtrandotherPLthEUR	271299	319645	84.88%
PLforperiodNetincomethEUR	219383	319645	68.63%
ExportrevenuethEUR	293951	319645	91.96%
MaterialcoststhEUR	275163	319645	86.08%
CostsofemployeesthEUR	235082	319645	73.54%
DepreciationAmortthEUR	217905	319645	68.17%
InterestpaidthEUR	248144	319645	77.63%
RDexpensesthEUR	309014	319645	96.67%
CashflowthEUR	236056	319645	73.85%
AddedvaluethEUR	263810	319645	82.53%
EBITDAthEUR	235223	319645	73.59%
Numberofemployees	215348	319645	67.37%

Table 15 - Missing information: Exits Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
CompanyID	0	3431	0%
AcqDealNumber	0	3431	0%
Acquirorname	8	3431	0.23%
Acquirorcountrycode	64	3431	1.87%
AcqDealtype	0	3431	0%
AcqDealvaluethEUR	1784	3431	52.00%
AcquirorBvDIDnumber	241	3431	7.02%
AcqDate	0	3431	0%
AcqYear	0	3431	0%
Acquisition_dummy	0	3431	0%
IPODealNumber	0	3431	0%
IPODealvaluethEUR	49	3431	1.43%

IPODate	27	3431	0.79%
IPOYear	27	3431	0.79%
IPOStockExchange	124	3431	3.61%
IPO_dummy	0	3431	0%

Table 16 – Missing information: Equity CF Investments

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
IDEquityCF	0	750	0%
CampaignName	0	750	0%
EquityOfferedFirstCampaign	44	750	17.6%
PostMoneyFirstCampaign	44	750	17.6%
CampaignDate	0	750	0%
CampaignYear	0	750	0%
CampaignAmountRaised	3	750	0.4%
CampaignCategory	242	750	32.27%
Platform	0	750	0%
CompanyID	0	750	0%

3 Technical Specifications

3.1 Information on the data base system

The database is currently available in .csv and STATA (.dta) format.

3.2 Description of the Entity Relationship Model (if applicable)

Not applicable.

3.3 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures (if applicable)

The VICO dataset is integrated into the RISIS Core Facility (RCF) with other firm-level RISIS databases. In particular, integration is made possible through the use of FirmReg, a register that uniquely identifies and tracks over time companies included in different RISIS datasets, such as CIB on the largest innovative industrial firms worldwide, Cheetah on European mid-size fast growing firms and VICO. Each VICO company is connected to FirmReg through unambiguous and stable (over time) identifiers.

At the geographical level, VICO is harmonized with the other research infrastructures in RISIS by adopting the RISIS Cortext geocoding service, NUTS classification of administrative units (as provided by Eurostat) and the Functional Urban and Rural Areas classification (as provided by the OECD).

Integration of VICO in the RCF will be allowed with anonymised company names, which is essential for legal issues due to data retrieval from different commercial databases. Only in specific cases when a high level of data protection is guaranteed, such as in case of physical visits and direct research collaborations with the datasets' owners, companies' names may be disclosed.

4 Scientific use cases and main references

Given the fine-grained and wide scope of data on VC-backed firms, VICO can be used to produce large scale evidence on the ecology of the VC landscape in Europe, extending current empirical evidence based on the previous version of the dataset. In particular, promising avenues of research include:

1. Investment patterns and selection process (see Bertoni et al., 2015a; Colombo and Shafi, 2016), e.g. European v. US VCs' peculiar investment criteria, how different types of VCs select their portfolio firms;
2. The treatment effect on invested companies (Croce et al., 2013; Grilli and Murtinu, 2014; Colombo and Murtinu, 2017; Cumming et al., 2017), e.g. the effect of VC value added activities on portfolio firms' performance (e.g. growth, innovation, access to subsequent funding), the specific treatment effect of different types of VCs;
3. The certification effect and removal of financial constraints of portfolio firms (e.g. Guerini and Quas, 2016; Bertoni et al., 2015b);
4. The internationalization and geography of VC activity in Europe (Devigne et al., 2013; Bertoni and Groh, 2014), e.g. the emergence and/or agglomeration of VC markets around big metropolitan areas, the attraction of cross-border investments.

Moreover, the broad longitudinal timeframe (1998-2018) gives the opportunity to study the effects of the financial crisis on VC activity, while the coverage of different types of investors, in addition to VCs (e.g., BAs) allows to investigate the complementarities between VCs and other sources of finance.

In what follows, we provide an overview of a selection of published and working papers based on VICO.

Guerini and Tenca (2018) provides evidence about the geographical concentration of VC activity in seven European countries. The work presents the geographical distribution of VC investments and VC-backed technology-intensive start-ups, analysing the regional and country-level factors associated to the regional concentration of VC activity. Results from econometric estimates suggest that regional VC activity is positively associated to the level of regional knowledge intensity, the level of regional human capital, the local supply of VC investors and a favourable country's legal and institutional environment.

Croce et al. (2018) study how cultural distance between entrepreneurial ventures and prospective VC investors affects the likelihood of investment realization. Whilst other scholars addressed this question by investigating whether and how cross-country cultural distance affects cross-border VC investments, sub-country measures of cultural distance are used to extend the analysis to domestic investments. Based on a unique database of VC investments in European entrepreneurial ventures during the period 1998-2014, results show that sub-national cultural distance is negatively associated to the likelihood of investment realization. Furthermore, domestic VC investments are more affected by cultural distance than cross-border investments.

Guerini and Hong (2018) examine whether there are positive externalities associated with US VC firms' presence in the European market. The study focuses on how the presence of US VC firms in the local market affects performances of start-ups backed by domestic investors. Specifically, the authors use VICO to investigate if entry of foreign VC firms has an additional indirect impact on the performance of start-ups backed by domestic investors. Results suggest

that domestic VC firms can obtain valuable know-how through forming syndicates with foreign VC firms. Prior experience with US VC firms is associated to greater performance of domestic VC investments.

Colombo et al (2017) empirically test the monitoring effect of VC financing on portfolio companies. Using the introduction of a new airline route between investor and investee locations as an exogenous shock lowering the cost of monitoring activities performed by a VC, the authors assess the treatment effect of VC on portfolio companies' performances in terms of the likelihood of being listed or acquired, the number of patents, the number of employees and the amount of sales. Results show that VC monitoring has a positive and economically relevant effect on European portfolio companies along most of these performance measures, but with different time horizons.

Block et al. (2018) investigate how VCs' specialized expertise and the fit between investor expertise and firm characteristics affect investors' ability to add value to start-ups. Using a unique longitudinal dataset on European venture financing and performance and robust econometric techniques, the authors find that greater relative specialization negatively affects investors' value-add. Moreover, the study finds that greater specialization can be helpful for investor value-add in late-stage investments. Nonetheless, results suggest that greater relative specialization improves VC selection skills and thus can be a reasonable investment strategy for VC investors.

Camerani and Guerini (2018) study the impact that the 2008 financial crisis had on the economic growth and survival of small high tech firms. In particular, the study also considers how sectors and countries have been differently affected by the crisis. Finally, this study looks at the role of different kinds of VC investments in alleviating the effects of the financial crisis. The analyses suggest that the crisis affected VC industry differently in terms of sector, geographical patterns (with an increase of the local bias of VC investments) and sources of VC financing.

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